

Effect of Russia Ukraine War on the Indian Stock Market: An Event Study Approach

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Abstract: The study identifies the Indian Stock market's reaction to the Russia-Ukraine War on February 24, 2022. The event study methodology is adopted to identify the sectoral impact of the war on the Indian stock market. The fear of raw materials and disruptions in the payments with Russian companies with an increase in NPAs have affected the Auto, Banking, and Financial Services sectors negatively and these sectors have reported significant negative abnormal returns in the anticipation and adjustment window. The metal, pharma, and energy sectors posted a negative abnormal return in the anticipation window, but post the event in the adjustment window, the sectors reported significant positive abnormal returns. With the imposed restrictions on Russian companies, these sectors are expected to turn attractive hoping to capture the market share which has made investors go bullish towards these sectors. The FMCG and IT sectors are not much impacted due to the event. The AAR and CAAR show that overall, the Indian stock market reacted negatively to the news of the War prior to the event. But later on, the stock market recovered from the fall and reported a near-zero abnormal return 10 days post the event date.

Originality/Value: To the best of the author's knowledge, this study is one of the earliest studies to analyse the effect of Russia Ukraine War on the Indian Stock Market. Policymakers, investors, and other important stakeholders will find the study's conclusions useful in developing solutions that will lessen the impact of geopolitical risks on stock markets.

Keywords: Abnormal Returns, Event study, Geo-Political Risk, Indian Stock Market, Russia Ukraine War, Sectoral Indices

JEL: G12, G14, G11

1. Introduction

The Russia-Ukraine war which started on 24th February 2022 and the resultant uncertainties have created instabilities across the economies worldwide. The academic literature (Leigh, Wolfers and Zitzewitz) (Choudhry) has studied war as one of the significant events which have created uncertainty among investors and have contributed to variations in stock prices. It is widely known that nations and their economies are interconnected in such a way that they rely on one another for a variety of things, including oil, trade, services, investments, and so forth. Therefore, any significant geopolitical event anywhere in the world could have an effect on markets in other nations. As studied by (Caldara and Iacoviello, Measuring Geopolitical Risk) geopolitical risk affects the business cycles and financial markets and is one of the major factors' investors consider before making any investment decisions. One of the effects of the war is the rising inflation and commodity prices which resulted in increased crude oil, metal, and edible oil prices. The effects of globalization include increasing obstacles to international trade and transportation, mostly isolating Russia. In addition, sanctions against Russian gas have a negative impact on the world's energy supplies. For example, establishing supply chains for liquefied natural gas might encourage the development of local energy sources like coal and green energy. Alternatively, it can encourage the expansion of global trade. Adaptations to long-term energy and food supply plans are being driven by the situation in Ukraine. In addition, there are numerous grounds to assume that Ukraine's conflict will impact global markets, with shifting patterns of economic globalization—both expanding and contracting—in various national settings playing a key influencing role.

In this context, the study is focused on studying the impact of the Russia Ukraine war on the Indian stock market. Investors, portfolio managers, and regulators should pay close attention to the effects of wars on the equity markets. The study, therefore, aim to provide empirical evidence relating to how various sectors of the Indian stock market responded to the news of the Russia and Ukraine War. For the study, the event study methodology is adopted. The event study methodology was developed to look into how unexpected events affect stock values. For each sector in the sample, a market model is estimated as part of a conventional event study, and the related abnormal returns are then calculated. According to the efficient-market hypothesis, these extraordinary returns may be a reflection of how the stock market has responded to the impending occurrence of the expected event.

2. Literature Review

One of the earliest works in the event study methodology was adopted by (Dolley) where he studies nominal price fluctuations at the time of the split to analyse the price implications of stock splits. Over the decades, many new studies have evolved in the event study

methodology. (Myers and Bakay) (Barker, 1956) (Baker) (Ashley) are the studies that came up during the period. Among the changes were the elimination of overall stock market price swings and the separation of conflicting events. The methodology used now was established in key studies by (Fama, Fisher, Jensen, & Roll, 1969) and (Ball & Brown, 1968) in the late 1960s. Ball and Brown examined the informational value of earnings, and Fama and colleagues examined the impacts of stock splits after controlling for the impact of concurrent dividend increases. Numerous improvements have been created in the years after these ground-breaking researches. These alterations involve design changes to account for more exact hypotheses and challenges brought on by deviations from the statistical assumptions utilized in the earlier study. The work of Brown & Warner, published in 1980 and 1985, has a practical significance for many of the issues and adjustments. The 1985 paper deals with challenges for daily data, while the 1980 work discusses technical challenges for data sampled at a monthly period. The methodology of the event study is widely published by various authors (Binder, 1998) (J. J. Binder, On the Use of the Multivariate Regression Model in Event Studies) (McWilliams and Siegel) (MacKinlay).

The event study methodology is widely used to study the market responses to various events. The response of the market towards regulatory enforcement was looked into by (Carroll and Lamdin) (Whinston and Collins) (Dohlman, Hall and Somwaru) (J. J. Binder) (Boardman, Vertinsky and Whistler), (Arora) (Bruno, Onali and Schaeck). The event study methodology is also widely used in investigating the market reactions to events like stock splits (Fama, Fisher, Jensen, & Roll, 1969) (Wu and Chan) (Grinblatt, Masulis and Titman) (Conroy and Harris) (Aduda and Chemarum) (Armitage), (Sivashanmugam., Krishna and Karthik) mergers and acquisitions (Liargovas and Repousis) (Dilshad) (Rani, Yadav and Jain) (Yoo, Lee and Heo) (Simões, Macedo-Soares and Klotzle) dividend announcement (Suwanna) (Maitra and Dey) (Sharma) (Aamir and Shah) (Rosario and Chavali) (Mehndiratta and Gupta) (Ngoc & Cuong, 2016) (Pandey and Kumari) (Seyedimany) (Robiyanto and Yunitaria) (TANVEER and JAMIL) (Poornima, Morudkar and Reddy) change in the board members of the company (Kang, Ding, & Charoenwong, 2009) (Lee and James) (Yermack) and various other events like product recalls (Zhao, Li and Flynn) (KELEŞ & ÜLENGİN 2019) (Chu, Lin and Prather) , (Ni, Flynn and Jacobs), advertising campaigns etc. (Agrawal and Kamakura) (MATHUR and MATHUR) (Wiles and Danielova)

In this paper the researcher is going to look into the Indian market reaction towards the Russia Ukraine War. The invasion of Russia towards Ukraine started on 24th February 2022. Numerous empirical findings demonstrate that military conflicts or geopolitical tensions always echo and resonate throughout the world's stock markets. It is widely known that nations and their economies are interconnected in that they rely on one another for a variety of things, including oil, commerce, services, investments, and so forth. Therefore, any

significant geopolitical event anywhere in the world could have an effect on markets in other nations. (Kollias, Manou, Papadamou, & Stagiannis, 2011) look at how the stock markets in Madrid and London were affected by the bombings. In most of the sectors in Spain but not in London, a sizable abnormal return was discovered. Additionally, they find that the bombings had a momentary impact on returns and volatility and that the London market rebounded far more swiftly than Spanish markets. (Eldor and Melnick) demonstrate using a time-series approach that financial markets are effective at pricing the shocks associated with terrorist strikes. (Károlyi and Martell) examine how terrorist strikes affect stock prices and demonstrate that losses are greater when the targets are in more developed or wealthy nations. Using an event study approach, (Chen and Siems) analyse how terror affects global capital markets and find that the U.S. capital markets recover from terrorist strikes more quickly than other global capital markets. The resilience is attributed to the healthy banking and financial sector, which provides enough liquidity to foster market stability and reduce panic among investors. (Rigobon and Sack) discover that the US equity market is negatively impacted by the probability of an Iraqi war, therefore calculating war risk is helpful in predicting how stock values will change during a conflict. (Memdani and Shenoy) assert that stock market declines are brought on by terrorist strikes. (Bailey and Chung) (Balcilar, Bonato and Demirer) (Caldara and Iacoviello, *Measuring Geopolitical Risk*) asserts that geopolitical risks not only have a significant impact on the growth and excess returns of local stock markets, but they also have an impact on global markets. (Salisu, Ogbonna and Lasisi) finds that emerging stock market volatility responds more positively to geopolitical risks. (Boungou and Yatié) found in their study that the stock markets demonstrated a negative and considerable impact of the war between Russia and Ukraine on global stock performance. The effect was worse with countries in proximity to Russia and Ukraine. The crisis between Russia and Ukraine was examined by (Yousaf, Patel and Yaroyaya) using an event study approach in the G20 and other chosen stock markets. They concluded that the day of the invasion showed a significant negative impact of this military operation on the bulk of the stock markets, particularly the Asian and European markets. In the turbulent two weeks that followed the invasion, (Tosun and Eshraghi) looked at how the financial market react to the announcement of companies in Russia. They observed increased trading activity and selling pressure, as well as the difficulty of reaching any sensible decisions when political unrest was present. Geopolitical risk and systemic risk in the commodity markets during the Ukraine War were researched by (Wang, Bouri and Fareed). The study states that high level of return spillovers is associated with geo political risk. According to (Mbah and Wasum), this crisis is starting to have an effect on the world economy. The dramatic rise in the price of food, natural gas, and oil that was seen just a few days after this crisis began has contributed to the ongoing inflation that is already wreaking havoc on the majority of world economies. The result is that the global economy is being negatively impacted by household

spending, rising uncertainty, erratic stock fluctuations, supply chain disruptions, skyrocketing electricity costs, declining investment owing to political risks, and economic growth hindrances. On the announcement that Russia has declared war on Ukraine, the Sensex and Nifty 50 fell by approximately 3.5 percent in early trade on 24th February 2022. Oil prices, which have been steadily climbing in due to the crisis in Russia and Ukraine, surpassed \$100 per barrel due to concern that sanctions would affect Russia's shipment of crude oil. Given that India imports more than 80% of its oil needs, the development is a significant setback for the nation. This study aims to conduct a preliminary analysis of how the Russia-Ukraine war has affected the Indian stock market. The study adds to the limited event studies in the literature that look at sectoral analysis of how war affects the financial markets. Policy makers, investors, and other important stakeholders will find the study's conclusions useful in developing solutions that will lessen the impact of geopolitical risks on stock markets.

The rest of the paper are structured as follows. The description of data and the methodologies used in the study are presented in Section 3. The Analysis and the discussion of findings are presented in the Section 4. Finally, Section 5 summarises the study and gives a conclusions and directions of future scope of study.

3. Data and Methodology

This study covers the daily closing prices of eight of India's Sectoral Indices: Nifty Auto, Nifty Bank, Nifty Energy, Nifty IT, Nifty Financial Services, Nifty FMCG, Nifty Metal and Nifty Pharma. The sample period is from June 1, 2021, to March 31, 2022. The event research methodology is used to examine whether any notable abnormal returns exist both before and after the start of the war. The data required for the study are downloaded from the website "investing.com". The Nifty 50 index is used as a proxy for calculating market performance since it is a true representation of a market with 50 actively traded stocks. The market model was used in this study to assess the impact of the Russia-Ukraine War. Among other models the OLS market model is found to be providing better results (Dyckman, Philbrick and Stephan) (MacKinlay) Hence the study has used market model for conducting event study.

The study utilizes an estimation period, which in our case is 120 days, to calculate the sample sectors' normal returns. An event window is used to calculate the abnormal price fluctuations for the selected sectors. The event window in this study consists of 21 trading days, 10 days prior to the event (anticipation window), and 10 days after the event (adjustment window). The daily stock and market returns are calculated using the formula:

$$R_s = \log (P_{st} / P_{st-1}) \quad \dots(1)$$

$$R_m = \log (P_{mt} / P_{m t-1}) \quad \dots(2)$$

The alpha and beta are calculated using the Ordinary Least-squares method by regressing sectoral returns over market returns over the estimation period. Then the expected return is calculated using the formula:

$$\text{Expected Return} = \alpha + \beta \times R_m \quad \dots (3)$$

After getting the expected and actual return, the abnormal or excess return is calculated by taking the difference between the actual and expected return. The excess or abnormal return is calculated by:

$$\text{Abnormal Return} = \text{Actual Return} - \text{Expected Return} \quad \dots(4)$$

The Cumulative Abnormal Return CAR is computed by taking the summation of average Abnormal Return in the respective event window

$$CAR_t = \sum_{t=-10}^{t=+10} AR_{i,t} \dots (5)$$

In addition to the CAR technique, which is considered to be descriptive in nature, the BHAR approach, which is accompanied with a more feasible strategy, was also adopted. The formula for calculating a stock's BHAR is one plus each month's AR minus one, which is computed as follows:

$$r_{st} = \prod_{s=t-1}^{t2} (1 + r_{st}) - 1 \dots (6)$$

$$r_{mt} = \prod_{t=t-1}^{t2} (1 + r_{mt}) - 1 \dots (7)$$

$$BHAR = r_{st} - r_{mt}$$

The Average Abnormal Return (AAR) is obtained by averaging cross-sectionally, the abnormal returns of sectoral indices for each day of the event period.

$$ARR_t = \sum_{i=1}^N AR_{i,t} \dots (8)$$

The AAR is then cumulated to get a Cumulative Average Abnormal Return

$$CAAR_t = \sum_{i=t1}^{t2} AR_t \dots (9)$$

The methodology followed by (Brown and Warner, 1985) is adopted in this study where he uses the t-test to assess the significance of AARs and CAARs on all of the trading days throughout the event window to determine whether or not they are significant. The t statistics are calculated as follows:

$$t = \frac{AAR_t}{Standard\ Error} \dots (10)$$

To determine the statistical significance of abnormal returns associated with the war, the standard t-test is performed. To evaluate whether the results are statistically different from zero, t-scores are computed in MS Excel.

4. Data Analysis and Discussion

The return series for each sectoral indices and the market index is generated using the equation (1) and (2) for the estimation period and the event window. Then the sectoral returns are regressed with the market index to obtain the intercept (α) and slope (β). The details of alpha and beta coefficients are shown in table no: 1 below:

Table No. 1: The alpha and beta values of Nifty Sectoral Indices in the estimation window

Indices	Alpha	Beta
Nifty Auto	0.0012	0.9925
Nifty Bank	0.0003	1.0257
Nifty FMCG	-0.0008	0.7379
Nifty Financial Services	-0.0003	1.0434
Nifty Pharma	-0.0006	0.5717
Nifty IT	0.0001	1.0514
Nifty Metal	0.0004	1.4113
Nifty Energy	0.0015	0.9698

When compared to an appropriate benchmark index, an investment's performance is measured by its alpha. In our analysis, Nifty FMCG, Nifty Financial Services, and Nifty Pharma have negative alpha values, showing that these sectors are slightly underperforming compared to the market during the estimation period. Beta is a metric used in statistics to compare a stock's volatility to that of the market as a whole. Our analysis shows that the Nifty bank, financial services, IT, and Metal sectors are more volatile than the market. The metal sector is the most volatile sector with 41% more volatility than the market.

As information leakage is possible a few days before the event, we take the event window as 10 days before the event (Anticipation window) and 10 days after the event (Adjustment Window). In addition, we also consider 3 event windows: (-1,1), (-5,5), (-10,10). Table no: 2 exhibits the abnormal returns of selected sectors of nifty during the period.

Table No: 2 CAR and BHAR for sectoral indices of Nifty

Nifty Auto	Market Model						Nifty Bank	Market Model					
	0	(-10,-1)	(1,10)	(-1,1)	(-5,5)	(-10,10)		0	(-10,-1)	(1,10)	(-1,1)	(-5,5)	(-10,10)
AAR	-1.64%	-2.02%	-9.46%	-1.74%	-9.87%	-13.12%	AAR	-0.92%	-1.10%	-4.55%	0.06%	-3.47%	-6.57%
SD	0.010	0.003	0.003	0.006	0.003	0.002	SD	0.007	0.002	0.002	0.004	0.002	0.002
t stat	-1.585	-6.170	-28.948	-2.923	-31.668	-58.153	t stat	-1.309	-4.939	-20.541	0.145	-16.423	-42.923
BHAR	-1.64%	-2.01%	-9.12%	-1.74%	-9.48%	-12.40%	BHAR	-0.92%	-1.10%	-4.50%	0.05%	-3.45%	-6.42%
SD	0.010	0.003	0.003	0.006	0.003	0.002	SD	0.007	0.002	0.002	0.004	0.002	0.002
t stat	-1.585	-6.158	-27.893	-2.920	-30.413	-54.999	t stat	-1.309	-4.980	-20.278	0.127	-16.302	-41.945
Nifty FMCG	Market Model						Nifty Financial Services	Market Model					
	0	(-10,-1)	(1,10)	(-1,1)	(-5,5)	(-10,10)		0	(-10,-1)	(1,10)	(-1,1)	(-5,5)	(-10,10)
AAR	0.28%	-0.05%	1.60%	0.45%	0.39%	1.83%	AAR	-0.13%	0.29%	-4.27%	0.28%	-1.64%	-4.11%
SD	0.006	0.002	0.002	0.004	0.002	0.001	SD	0.005	0.002	0.002	0.003	0.002	0.001
t stat	0.444	-0.244	8.119	1.237	2.089	13.447	t stat	-0.253	1.753	-25.508	0.921	-10.296	-35.583
BHAR	0.28%	-0.05%	1.59%	0.45%	0.39%	1.81%	BHAR	-0.13%	0.29%	-4.21%	0.28%	-1.65%	-4.07%
SD	0.006	0.002	0.002	0.004	0.002	0.001	SD	0.005	0.002	0.002	0.003	0.002	0.001
t stat	0.444	-0.268	8.042	1.236	2.062	13.326	t stat	-0.253	1.706	-25.164	0.919	-10.336	-35.213
Nifty Pharma	Market Model						Nifty IT	Market Model					
	0	(-10,-1)	(1,10)	(-1,1)	(-5,5)	(-10,10)		0	(-10,-1)	(1,10)	(-1,1)	(-5,5)	(-10,10)
AAR	-0.88%	-2.58%	6.29%	1.26%	-1.96%	2.83%	AAR	0.43%	-0.15%	5.71%	0.74%	4.86%	5.99%
SD	0.009	0.003	0.003	0.005	0.003	0.002	SD	0.010	0.003	0.003	0.006	0.003	0.002
t stat	-0.994	-9.231	22.485	2.462	-7.366	14.651	t stat	0.429	-0.483	18.073	1.291	16.132	27.458
BHAR	-0.88%	-2.57%	6.41%	1.24%	-1.98%	2.77%	BHAR	0.43%	-0.18%	5.77%	0.75%	4.94%	6.03%
SD	0.009	0.003	0.003	0.005	0.003	0.002	SD	0.010	0.003	0.003	0.006	0.003	0.002
t stat	-0.994	-9.173	22.905	2.437	-7.440	14.325	t stat	0.429	-0.568	18.266	1.294	16.392	27.677
Nifty Metal	Market Model						Nifty Energy	Market Model					
	0	(-10,-1)	(1,10)	(-1,1)	(-5,5)	(-10,10)		0	(-10,-1)	(1,10)	(-1,1)	(-5,5)	(-10,10)
AAR	1.44%	-3.61%	11.89%	4.00%	12.30%	9.72%	AAR	-0.64%	-0.74%	4.91%	-0.35%	5.06%	3.54%
SD	0.013	0.004	0.004	0.008	0.004	0.003	SD	0.008	0.003	0.003	0.005	0.002	0.002
t stat	1.076	-8.505	28.002	5.162	30.387	33.184	t stat	-0.775	-2.837	18.926	-0.736	20.439	19.764
BHAR	1.44%	-3.59%	12.05%	4.05%	12.76%	9.59%	BHAR	-0.64%	-0.77%	4.95%	-0.35%	5.09%	3.48%
SD	0.013	0.004	0.004	0.008	0.004	0.003	SD	0.008	0.003	0.003	0.005	0.002	0.002
t stat	1.076	-8.460	28.391	5.221	31.513	32.730	t stat	-0.775	-2.949	19.058	-0.740	20.576	19.434

In multiple event windows, the auto sector displayed a sizable negative abnormal return. In the anticipation window (-10, -1), a negative abnormal return of -2.02% was recorded, and in the adjustment window (1,10), a negative abnormal return of -9.46% was observed. This demonstrates that the industry has responded adversely, and the effects have only intensified since the event. A negative abnormal return was similarly recorded by the event windows of (-1,1), (-5,5), and (-10,10). BHAR was also computed to test the results' robustness; it too produced results that were comparable, with the adjustment window reporting a bigger negative abnormal return than the anticipation window. As a result, it may be said that the event had a detrimental impact on the auto sector. Furthermore, the banking industry reported a lower positive CAR (-1.10%) in the anticipation window compared to the adjustment window's (-4.55%). This demonstrates that following the event, investors in this industry had a pessimistic perspective. BHAR was also computed to test the result's robustness, and it produced results that were similar. A negative statistically significant abnormal return was visible in the returns for the event windows (-5, 5) and (-10, 10). In

the anticipation window, the FMCG industry did not record any notable abnormal returns. The adjustment window reported a statistically significant positive CAR and BHAR. A statistically significant positive abnormal return was also found for this event window of (-10,10). The adjustment window for the financial services sector revealed a statistically significant negative CAR and BHAR, indicating that the sector had been negatively impacted after the event. The anticipation window for this sector did not indicate any significant CAR or BHAR. Event windows (-5,5) and (-10,10) indicated a substantial negative abnormal return, however the shorter event window (-1,1) did not record any significant abnormal return. Pharma reported a negative abnormal return in the anticipation window, but after the event the sector recovered and recorded a large CAR of 6.29% and BHAR of 6.41% in the adjustment window. A positive CAR was reported by the industry during the event window of (10,10). The IT industry responded well to the event, reporting a favourable abnormal return on the event windows of (-1,1), (-5,5) and (-10,10). In the expectation window, when investors had a bearish outlook on the market, the metal and energy sectors also experienced negative abnormal returns. However, following the incident, the sectors recovered and recorded abnormally positive returns.

The sector-wise impact showed that the Auto sector was impacted more by the war. This can be related to concerns about raw material shortages, such as those for Memory and sensor chips, which are essential to the manufacture of automobiles. Another factor is the worry that neon gas, which is used to manufacture the semiconductors used in automobiles and of which Ukraine is the world's largest producer and exporter, would run out. Russia is the world's largest producer of palladium, a vital component in the creation of memory and sensor chips. This has a detrimental impact on the auto industry. The banking sector also reported a significant negative return, which can be contributed to the imposed restrictions on Russian businesses. This will contribute to shortages of commodities, disruptive logistics, and resulting NPAs. The metal sector reported a significant positive abnormal return during the event window (-1,1) and (-5,5). With restrictions on Russian exports worldwide, the Indian metal sector is expected to turn attractive and is hoping to capture the export market share. This made investors go bullish on this sector. Since the war began in February 2022, the price of crude oil has surpassed \$100 per barrel, which has benefited energy businesses involved in oil exploration and export. Indian pharmaceutical firms may have the chance to take the position of Western producers quitting the Russian market as a result of the various sanctions the US has implemented. This has created a bullish trend in the pharma sector and positive abnormal return was reported in the sector for the event window (-10,10). The result is comparable with the studies of (Boubaker, Goodell and Pandey), (Sun, Song and Zhang) where the authors have opined those globalized countries and countries with proximity to Russia and Ukraine are more affected by the war than other countries.

Table No: 3 The Average Abnormal Returns and Cumulative Average Abnormal return in the event window.

	AAR						CAAR					
	(-10,-1)	0	(-1,1)	(-5,5)	(-10,10)	(1,10)	(-10,-1)	0	(-1,1)	(-5,5)	(-10,10)	(1,10)
AAR	-1.24%	-0.26%	0.59%	0.71%	0.01%	1.51%	-7.7%	-1.5%	-3.56%	-8.9%	-10.5%	-1.33%
SD	0.0009	0.0028	0.0016	0.0008	0.0006	0.0009	0.0020	0.0064	0.0037	0.0019	0.0014	0.0020
t statistics	-14.05	-0.918	3.632	8.387	0.229	17.110	-37.57	-2.331	-9.585	-45.88	-74.60	-6.530

The AAR in the anticipation window is found to be negative and statistically significant for the Indian stock market. The adjustment window reported a positive statistically significant abnormal return, which shows that the stock market bounced back from the initial loss and the market were able to generate positive abnormal return post the event. During the event window of (-1,1), (-5,5) a positive favourable abnormal return was seen for the Indian stock market.

The CAAR of the Indian stock market showed a negative abnormal return of -7.7% prior to the event. On the event day a negative statistically abnormal return was reported. The adjustment window revealed a statistically significant negative abnormal return of -1.33% post the event. This shows the market have adjusted to the initial loss and is able to recover some of the losses after the event. The sector wise study shows that each of the sector reacted differently to the event and the AAR and CAAR shows that the market has recovered from the initial fall and recovered some of its losses. A negative statistically significant CAAR was reported for the event window (-1,1), (-5,5) and (-10,10). At the 10th day after the event a near zero abnormal CAAR was reported.

Chart no: 1 Cumulative Abnormal Returns and Average Abnormal Returns in the event window

5. Conclusion

Using the event research approach, the impact of the Russian-Ukrainian war on the Indian stock market has been examined. Investors throughout the event window had a pessimistic outlook on the auto sector due to the expected shortage of raw materials, which led to a negative statistically significant abnormal return. The bans placed on Russian businesses and the ensuing delays in the payment system have been attributed for the Nifty bank's high negative abnormal return during the event window. The Nifty metal responded favourably to the event, reporting a substantial positive abnormal return for the event window of (-1,1) and (-5,5) with an optimistic outlook where corporations are trying to take market share in the world with enforced restrictions on Russian companies. The energy sector had a negative outlook prior to the event, but post the event the sector reported a positive return, thanks to India's neutral stand on Russia and Ukraine war. Overall, the market bounced back from the first decline and, by the event's tenth day, reported almost no abnormal returns. The study's findings will be helpful to policymakers, investors, and other key stakeholders in coming up with solutions that will decrease the effect of geopolitical risks on stock markets.

Limitations and Scope for Future Research

Since this study was one of the first to examine how the Russia-Ukraine War affected Indian stock markets, its findings provide information about the war's early effects. By using a larger sample period, future studies can concentrate on how the war has affected each sector.

Conflicts of Interest

The author has no conflict of Interest to disclose.

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